

STIMULATING THE GROWTH OF COMPETITIVENESS OF CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS**Leshchynsky V.***Doctor of Law,**Associate Professor of the Department
of Agricultural Economics and Management**Kyiv Agrarian University**National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine
Kyiv***Novykov D.***Postgraduate student**Kyiv National University of Civil Engineering and Architecture
Kyiv***Abstract**

This article examines the key issues related to stimulating construction organization restructuring. It identifies that the incentives include not only obvious crisis processes but also the desire to strengthen the construction company's competitive position in the target market. Timely restructuring can contribute to the creation of clear advantages over competitors in terms of product promotion and positioning. It is concluded that the restructuring of construction organizations requires the formation of a system of divisions: traditional management structure divisions; responsibility centers (cost centers, revenue centers, profit centers, and investment centers).

Keywords: competitiveness, construction companies, strategy.

An effectively functioning system for stimulating the growth of construction product competitiveness should ensure: activating innovative activities within the construction organization; stimulating demand for construction products; rationally leveraging economic potential; and ensuring the structural restructuring of the construction organization's management system. Stimulating demand for competitive construction products typically involves a combination of forms and methods that ensure increased sales volumes for market participants during the product's lifecycle.

Choosing the right goal for stimulating demand for construction products is a central aspect of managing the competitiveness of a construction organization. Moreover, if the goal of the incentive is to technically re-equip construction organizations to a new technological level, increasing the use of innovation, then it is necessary to adopt common solutions that apply equally to the entire construction industry. Therefore, stimulating the growth of construction product competitiveness is a function that primarily relates to strategic planning and management of the construction organization.

The choice of the goal for stimulating the growth of construction product competitiveness depends on the type of target audience. Thus, the goal of incentives applied to consumers of construction products is expressed in the form of increasing the number of buyers (customers), while the goal of incentives aimed at manufacturers of construction products is to enhance the motivational criteria of construction organization employees. If the task of restructuring and increasing the competitiveness of the construction industry is to be achieved, the incentive mechanism must include the selection of state priorities and a special mechanism for promoting these priorities. The choice of methods for stimulating the growth of construction product competitiveness depends on specific objectives. Various incentive methods can be grouped into the following: price incentives (sale at reduced prices, discounts); in-

kind incentives (bonuses, surcharges); and active incentives (customer competitions, corporate culture). The selection of a rational system for stimulating the growth of construction product competitiveness is of significant socioeconomic importance for every construction organization.

To achieve this goal, we believe it is advisable to apply a differentiated approach to stimulating the growth of construction product competitiveness, allowing for the potential impact of one type of incentive on various aspects of the construction organization's production activities. The system of measures to stimulate the growth of competitiveness in construction products based on a differentiated approach consists of the following elements. From the perspective of modern economic growth theory and practice, increasing the competitiveness of construction products is possible through maximum incentives for innovative activity among construction organizations. This goal is achieved through both direct investment and indirect incentives for investors, including through the provision of state guarantees. Thus, through the budget, the state stimulates final demand, facilitating the promotion of construction products on the market.

Research and successful solutions to the problem of increasing the competitiveness of construction products are inextricably linked to the selection of an incentive mechanism. The results of the research conducted, as well as the current market conditions, suggest the primary goal of stimulating demand growth in the construction market: mass housing construction across various segments, with varying price categories for purchasing and renting housing for the population, regardless of income level.

The study concludes that attracting affordable financial resources in the form of various types of preferential loans and subsidies provided as a form of government support can stabilize demand for housing. In addition to stimulating market processes through stable

demand, affordable financial resources, such as subsidies and loans, play an important role in the state's socioeconomic policy in terms of social protection and support for vulnerable categories of citizens unable to resolve their housing needs. As in other sectors of the economy, the progressive development of construction will be facilitated by a range of measures to modernize production, innovate, and improve personnel, stimulating the growth of competitive construction products. An important factor in supporting housing demand could be the inclusion in the cost of amounts paid to organizations to reimburse employees for interest on loans (credits) for the purchase and/or construction of residential premises.

Two criteria can be used to assess the technical feasibility of the incentive process: instrumental and economic. Economic criteria, by which all the above-mentioned objectives—the objects of incentives—are reduced, are meaningful only after the technical feasibility of implementing a management decision has been proven. While in production management, the technological feasibility of solutions is typically implied (or not clearly expressed), in innovation management it comes to the forefront, representing the defining value of the first stage of the innovation life cycle, which actually begins the incentive process as a tool for increasing the competitiveness of manufactured products. Based on this, the general criterion for the effectiveness of stimulating the growth of competitiveness of construction products should be considered the degree of achievement of a specific goal - the implementation of the innovative capabilities of a construction organization to organize the production of competitive products.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to fulfill one important condition: motivating employees to achieve the goals of the construction organization, ensuring an increase in the competitiveness of the manufactured products.

Employee stimulation as a method is expressed by their motivation in the form of compensation for labor. Previously, there was the concept of "stimulation", which is currently understood from an economic point of view as "motivation". This substitution of the concepts of the motivational process led to employees focusing on short-term economic goals, which hindered personal development and did not stimulate the need-motivational basis of the employee's personality, which is the most important reserve for increasing the competitiveness of products [11].

Due to the connection with necessity, motive serves as a motivator for a person to act and gives meaning to individual actions, goals, and the conditions for their achievement. Motive is based on cognitive needs, based on the fact that many products meet the human need for new knowledge [14]. "... The motivational process can be represented as a series of successive stages: awareness of employee needs; selection of the best way to receive a certain type of reward; decision on its implementation; "implementation of an action; receipt of a reward; satisfaction of a need" [2].

Experience shows that improving the operational efficiency of organizations through the development of a corporate culture system characterized by elements of

an innovative culture, the state of receptivity to innovation by individuals, groups, and society as a whole, and their readiness and ability to implement innovations, holds the potential for increased competitiveness.

The development of a corporate culture through a construction organization's management system can be viewed as a simulation tool, as it achieves a positive influence on motivation, employee receptivity to new ideas, and their readiness and ability to support and implement innovations. Corporate culture can act as a force that permeates employees' consciousness about the need to implement technological, organizational, and other innovations that enhance the competitiveness of their products and, consequently, the construction organization. Certainly, profit sharing systems should play a special role in motivating employees of construction organizations. This flexible component of wages has determined the relationship between the average level of employee remuneration and the final performance of construction organizations. The two primary objectives of profit sharing systems are: motivating employees to achieve high profits as the primary outcome of their activities; and reducing the conflict between the interests of employees and the organization's co-owners.

However, all things being equal, the organizational and economic mechanism for stimulating growth in the competitiveness of construction products must ensure the maintenance and subsequent growth of these competitiveness parameters by eliminating the influence of interference, leveling out deviations, and compensating for turbulence—that is, factors of the surrounding aggressive market environment.

Thus, the primary goal of a mechanism for stimulating the competitiveness of construction products is to align the entire set of resource potential elements with one another and, in the future, to provide organizational, technical, and economic pathways for the construction organization's transition from one fixed state to another, thereby ensuring a more stable market position.

Stimulating the growth of construction product competitiveness involves distributing strategic goals and objectives across organizational structure levels, departments, and implementers, which ensures:

1. Clearly defining the functional and line units that should focus on organizational support to achieve competitiveness goals. At the same time, the entire structure should be balanced in terms of the primary organizational management goal;

2. Verifying the homogeneity of each unit's goals to prevent a gap in responsibility for the same goal between departments;

3. Rational distribution of rights and responsibilities at different management levels based on a hierarchy of goals;

4. Establishing the sequence and nature of work to achieve ultimate goals;

5. Evaluating the effectiveness of various organizational decisions;

6. Developing performance-based assessment and incentive systems.

Tactical approaches to developing a management

system that creates opportunities to enhance the competitiveness of a construction organization can be recommended:

1. Construction organization managers create a neutral competitiveness management system. This stems from confidence in the design or technical excellence of their products, ensuring an advantage over competitors, and eliminating the need for additional reorganization of the organizational management structure. Although this approach is highly undesirable, it can yield the desired results for a construction organization if it can find a target segment or niche in the market. However, as soon as a construction organization begins to grow to increase production scale, the following may occur: the organization outgrows the established market segment in which it initially operated, and in another segment, it becomes a growing market and becomes attractive to other manufacturers. In this situation, measures must be taken to enhance the competitive advantages of construction products to outperform competitors in terms of price, production costs, quality, service level, etc.

2. Organization management creates "externally neutral" production systems. This implies full compliance of construction organizations with the standards established by their main competitors, i.e., they use similar equipment, technologies, and production organization and management methods. The management of such organizations will inevitably face the question: if they have different competitive advantages in the market than their main competitors, why is it necessary to adhere to the general production standards established in the industry?

3. Management begins to actively influence production systems, promoting their development and improvement. The production of competitive products is supported by all divisions of the construction organization. In this case, success will depend entirely on how effectively each construction organization utilizes similar equipment and technologies, and on the competitive advantages not only in the production structure but also in the management system. In other words, improving competitiveness becomes a function not so much of production as of management, and depends on the quality, management effectiveness, and organization of production in the broadest sense. This may include a more cost-effective management apparatus, greater decision-making efficiency, improved employee motivation, etc.

4. The production system in such construction organizations becomes, so to speak, "externally supported." Its effectiveness is determined not only by internal factors, such as management (production planning or quality management), but also by external factors (the quality of the organization and the effectiveness of the management system itself). Construction organizations that have achieved Level 4 competitiveness outperform their competitors in the market over the long term. They not only strive to replicate the experience of other organizations in the industry, not simply to surpass the strictest existing technical regulations and standards, but are ready to challenge any competitor in any aspect of production or management.

Developing effective management solutions is a

fundamental prerequisite for ensuring the competitiveness of a construction organization. This includes the following elements:

- Creating an effective team of professional managers;
- Forming organizational structures;
- Implementing an appropriate HR policy;
- Regulating socio-economic and psychological relationships within the organization;
- Creating a positive image of the organization, etc.

In practice, the best solution to a problem involves taking a new look at it, that is, finding a new alternative. Accordingly, the following stages of alternatives evaluation can be distinguished:

- Clarifying objectives and selecting them;
- Listing or inventing alternatives;
- Analyzing alternatives;
- Choosing the best solution;
- Presentation of results.

The analytical approach has five logical elements and stages:

- Location of objectives or goal setting;
- Identifying alternative means for achieving objectives;
- Resources for using each system;
- Construction of a mathematical model (in the operations research approach) or a logical model, i.e., a series of relationships between goals, alternative methods for achieving them, the environment, and resources;
- Selection of criteria for the preferred alternative.

An innovative approach to organizing incentives for the growth of a construction organization's competitiveness is associated, first and foremost, with isolating this system from the external environment and defining a set of consistent, logical steps that ensure the retention of achieved and the growth of competitive advantages over the long term.

In today's environment, the main strategic goal of virtually all construction organizations is maintaining sustainable competencies, achieved through the reform of organizational structures. Following a fundamental change in the external environment for construction organizations, the goals and objectives of incentives, and consequently, the material resources and organizational management structure, must change accordingly.

Restructuring a construction organization is characterized by aligning its organizational and production structure with the volume of production for which there is effective demand. This optimizes the cost-to-income ratio, ensuring product competitiveness and investment attractiveness, which entails changes in the production and management structure [5].

It should be noted that the primary goal of meso-level restructuring of the national economy is to increase the competitiveness of the corresponding level of industry or territorial organization. Micro-level restructuring is the process of adapting the internal structures of a construction organization, regardless of its size and legal form, to the constantly changing conditions of environmental development in order to achieve

greater sustainability and economic efficiency at minimal cost.

Organizational restructuring is a set of measures aimed at bringing the size of an enterprise and its divisions into line with the requirements of a competitive market environment. Restructuring even a single construction organization is complex, time-consuming, and requires significant financial and material resources, which requires the implementation of preventive measures [8].

Developing a preventive restructuring plan is the first step in implementing the basic procedure for developing a program to stimulate the growth of a construction organization's competitiveness. Preventive measures are designed to address key objectives such as reducing the likelihood of sales losses and mitigating the extent of damage. A construction company restructuring program should include the following sections:

- objectives and areas of restructuring;
- procedure and criteria for making restructuring decisions;
- funds required for the restructuring and financing mechanism;
- restructuring conditions;
- measures to facilitate restructuring;
- measures to ensure social protection for employees during restructuring;
- procedure for interaction with local authorities during the restructuring process;
- list of legal documents that support the specific restructuring method.

The restructuring program should be aimed at fostering a new vision and harnessing innovative ideas with the participation of all employees from the bottom up and across all structural units, thereby overcoming resistance to restructuring. This approach can be based on the extensive use of the unique advantages of team-based organizational structures. In this case, teams (target groups) are used both in the development and implementation of the restructuring program (as subjects of the restructuring process) and as the main structural units of the construction organization.

Restructuring at all levels of the production and economic activity of a construction organization is driven by the need to align (adapt) the internal organizational structure with the qualitatively changed conditions of the external competitive environment.

The depth and scope of restructuring may vary:

- partial restructuring, encompassing individual aspects of the construction organization or only one of them (major restructuring, changes to the organizational structure, management system, etc.);
- global or radical restructuring, encompassing all or almost all areas of the construction organization's economic activity, ensuring a transition to a new level of quality. However, the effect of restructuring is limited in time and depends on the depth and scale of the transformation, as well as the external and internal conditions of the construction organization, and can vary widely (usually from 2 to 3, 6, or 8 years). Therefore, partial, limited restructuring, which is often very effective, should not be contrasted with global restructuring, but, rather, can be considered a stage of a more comprehensive restructuring. The most typical, although

not exhaustive, objectives of restructuring include the following: development and introduction of new products; strengthening a competitive position; overcoming a crisis; and restoring solvency and financial stability.

Therefore, not only obvious crisis processes are an incentive for restructuring a construction organization, but also the desire to strengthen its competitive position in the target market. Timely restructuring can contribute to the creation of clear advantages over competitors in terms of product promotion and positioning methods.

Restructuring in construction organizations involves the formation of a system of divisions:

- 1) traditional departments of the management structure;
- 2) Responsibility centers (cost, revenue, profit, and investment centers).

The creation and effective management of responsibility centers is only possible with a clear definition of tasks and a division of competencies, which allows for the identification of those responsible for ensuring the construction organization's increased competitiveness. From a methodological perspective, we propose two alternative approaches to cross-functional solutions to emerging problems:

- 1) Use a formal structure (a center) to formulate the problem, analyze and collect data on it, and develop and test possible alternative solutions before reaching a final solution;

- 2) Apply a systems approach to business process reengineering (when choosing this method, the risks, dangers, and serious errors in implementing such a radical approach should be considered, especially if it is used as a tool for developing the construction organization and/or improving the competitiveness of its products).

The second method involves defining new business processes in accordance with general principles, specifying the mission and key goals of the organization, formulating the missions of divisions or departments, and listing key success factors that are necessary and sufficient to achieve increased competitiveness. As a result of the stimulating impact and restructuring, competitive construction products introduced to the market not only overcome its fundamental uncertainty, but also initiate effects on the target market segment, increasing the sustainability of the competitive advantages of construction organizations.

References

1. Konkurentospromozhnist pidpriumstva: navch. posib. / Dmytriiiev I.A. Kyrchata I.M. Shersheniuk O.M. - Kharkiv, 2020 – 340s. URL: <https://fmab.khadi.kharkov.ua/>
2. Kuzmin O.Ie. Konkurentospromozhnist pidpriumstva: planuvannia ta diahnostyka: /Monohrafiia/ O.Ie. Kuzmin, O.H. Melnyk, O.P. Romanko; za zah. red. d.e.n., prof. Kuzmina O.Ie. – Ivano-Frankivsk: IFNTUNH, 2017. – 180 s. URL: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/92533113.pdf>
3. S. M. Shkarlet, L. S. Ladonko, T. I. Korzh Metodolohichni aspekty ta metodychni pryntsyipy otsinky konkurentospromozhnosti syrorobnykh pidpriumstv // Naukovyi visnyk ChDIEU № 3 (11), 2011, s.

153-161. URL: <http://ir.stu.cn.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/9075/153-161.pdf>

4. Konkurentospromozhnist pidpriemstva: otsinka rivnia ta napriamy pidvyshchennia: [monohrafiia / za zah. red. O.H. Yankovoho]. – Odesa: Atlant, - 2013. – 470 s.

5. Konkurentospromozhnist pidpriemstva: navch. posib. / Lupak R. L., Vasylytsiv T. H. – Lviv: Vydavnytstvo LKA, 2016. – 484 s.

6. Partuta T. O., Fesenko T. V. Konkurentospromozhnist pidpriemstva ta mekhanizm yii zabezpechennia. Investytsii: praktyka ta dosvid. 2012. № 12. S. 91–96. URL: http://www.investplan.com.ua/pdf/12_2012/25.pdf

7. V. I. Dmytrenko, Suchasni umovy upravlinnia konkurentospromozhnistiu pidpriemstv budivelnoi haluzi. Efektyvna ekonomika № 4, 2017. URL: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=8141>

8. Minenko S.I. Mekhanizmy upravlinnia konkurentospromozhnistiu ahrarnykh pidpriemstv Ukrainy URL: https://khntusg.com.ua/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/dis_minenko-09.12.20.pdf

9. V. V. Loiko. M. V. Rudenko, V. S. Rudenko Dynamika rozvytku budivelnykh pidpriemstv Ukrainy ta mista Kyieva v konteksti zabezpechennia ekonomichnoi bezpeky URL: http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/pdf/7_2020/15.pdf

10. O. V. Romanenko, L. M. Alaverdian Ohliad stanu ta otsinka potentsialu rozvytku budivelnoi haluzi Ukrainy. URL: http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/pdf/4_2020/61.pdf

11. Mokhenko, A. S. Ekonomichna sutnist konkurentsii i konkurentospromozhnosti / A. S. Mokhenko // Tavriiskyi naukovyi visnyk. – Kherson, 2010. – № 68. – S. 165-171.

12. Lypych L. H. Formuvannia stratehii rozvytku budivelnoho pidpriemstva v umovakh investytsiinoi konkurentsii [Tekst]: monohrafiia / Liubov Hryhorivna

Lypych, Ihor Viktorovych Chornukha, Iryna Oleksandrivna Tsymbaliuk. – Lutsk: Vezha-Druk, 2015. – 212 s

13. Lych, V. and Kutsenko, A. (2022), “Essential characteristic of the competitiveness of a construction enterprise”, *Prostorovyi rozvytok*, no. 2, pp. 144-159.

14. Kramar, O.M. (2019), “Peculiarities of the impact of personnel provision on the results of the functioning of construction enterprises”, *Naukovi zapysky Lvivskoho universytetu biznesu ta prava. Seriya ekonomichna. Seriya yurydychna*, Iss. 23, pp. 42-47.

15. Pryhodko O., Kushnir I., Hrynenko I., Khomenko O. Innovative analytical and applied apparatus for modeling the organization of construction and development support of projects. International independent scientific journal. 2021. №34 (2). p.6- 11. ISSN 3547-2340 (Kraków, Rzeczpospolita Polska). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7061509>

16. Ryzhakova G. M. General-methodical regulation and analytical and information support of administration processes in the modern system of building development. Modern problems of architecture and urban planning. 2019. №55, C.154–168.

17. Kucherenko O., Ryzhakova, G., Chupryna K., Shpakova H., Kishchak N. Veremeev S. Scientific and applied components of the formation of the strategy of institutional-oriented diversification of construction enterprises. Management of development of complex systems. 2021. №47. C.109–118; <dx.doi.org/10.32347/2412-9933.2021.47.109-118>.

18. Chernyshev D., Ryzhakova G., Honcharenko T., Petrenko H., Chupryna I., Reznik N. Digital Administration of the Project Based on the Concept of Smart Construction. In: Alareeni, B., Hamdan, A. (eds) Explore Business, Technology Opportunities and Challenges. After the Covid-19 Pandemic. ICBT 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems. Springer, Cham. 2023. № 495. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-08954-1_114.